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THE ROLE OF MAGNESIUM IN PAIN

(Oral presentation)

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INTRODUCTION: Magnesium is the fourth most abundant essential ion in the human body. Magnesium plays a fundamental role in many cellular functions, such as metabolism, storage, energy utilization and has an important role in clinical medicine. Magnesium acts as an antagonist at the glutamate subtype of N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptors and blocks NMDA-induced currents in a voltage-dependent manner by blocking the receptor channel effects.

AIM: The aim of this study was to determine the usage of magnesium in analgesia in animals.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: Available databases were observed (Medline i Cochrane) for the period of preceding five years. Key words for searching were: experiments, animals, magnesium, analgesia, anesthesia.

RESULTS: Several lines of evidence indicate that magnesium enhances the analgesic effects of opioids, general and local anesthetics. NMDA receptors are important components of pain processing, and their response can be inhibited by ketamine and magnesium, which have a super-additive effect in combination. This may explain in part why analgesia is more effective for the combination than for either compound alone. As a sole drug magnesium demonstrated analgesic efficacy against acute, inflammatory and neuropathic pain in rats. Studies using formalin test in rats provided controversial data. In addition, accumulated evidence suggest link between inflammation and magnesium deficiency. The stimulation of NMDA receptors by glutamate is very important, not only for acute pain but also for chronic pain. The release of glutamate, substance P and CGRP in the spinal cord after nociceptive peripheral stimulation is essential in nociception. Magnesium modulates the release and action of all three neuromediators. Recently, it was demonstrated that low dose of magnesium sulphate added to morphine-ketamine combination administered systemically in rats produces a higher level of analgesia.

CONCLUSION: Magnesium is an antagonist of NMDA receptors and its role in analgesia has a therapeutic perspective.

Keywords: analgesia, therapeutic perspective